

Preliminary modelling of deep geothermal energy use in the Bécancour area (Québec)

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Abstract

Located in the St. Lawrence Lowlands sedimentary basin (Southern Québec), Bécancour is a populated area, hosting an industrial park. This project is to assess if using the deep saline aquifers (1 to 2 km deep) for heating purposes would be feasible. Uncertainty on the reservoir properties is the biggest hurdle for deep geothermal projects (e.g.: permeability, varies between 4×10^{-13} and 10^{-17} m^2 in the aquifers). Thus, efforts have been made to characterize the aquifers using vintage oil and gas wells in the area. New concepts of closed loops, standing column wells and doublets are being investigated to maximize efficiency.

1. Introduction

Geothermal heating from deep hydrothermal reservoirs is a reliable source of energy, enabling a reduction in greenhouse gases as well as economic growth (Jiang et al. 2019). Deep doublet systems have been used for half a century for district heating in the Paris Basin, France, showing sustainable performances over the long-term (Lopez et al. 2010). Deep closed loop systems (DBHE) have alternatively been developed in areas where formation permeability was insufficient for well doublets (Sapinska-Sliwa et al. 2016)

In Canada, geothermal energy is mostly used for heating and cooling purposes, including mostly shallow geothermal heat pump systems operated at low temperature (Raymond et al. 2015). Deep geothermal potential was studied with the aim of developing power plants (Majorowicz & Grasby 2010; Minea & Majorowicz 2012; Hofmann et al. 2014; Bédard et al. 2016; Richard et al. 2016). However, few studies have considered the heating potential for heating from hydrothermal resources at moderate depth (1 to 2 km).

The Bécancour area, selected for this study, is located in the St Lawrence Lowlands in southern Québec (Canada). This study area was chosen because there are potential large consumers for heat. Moreover, several oil and gas exploration wells were drilled in this area, whose data will be available for this project. The St. Lawrence Lowlands have additionally been studied for their geothermal

(Gauchat 2017; Bédard et al. 2018) and CO₂ sequestration potentials (eg:Ngoc et al. 2014).

2. Methods

Preliminary models have already been built within the framework of this study. The performance of 1215 m deep open loop targeting the Cairnside unit and 1500 m deep U tubes DBHE designs were compared to heat an industrial building (set heat requirements). They were developed to test the types of deep geothermal heat exchangers that could be implemented in this area, their requirements and expected performances.

For these preliminary models, all geological units of the St. Lawrence Lowlands were considered homogeneous and horizontal. The depth, unit permeability and brine properties were based on work by eg:Tran Ngoc et al. (2014). Thermal conductivity, heat capacity and density of the different units were defined according to (Bédard et al. 2018) .

Models were run in 3D using the FEFLOW finite element software, assuming a constant surface temperature of 8 °C, and constant bottom temperature calculated using the temperature gradient found in Tran Ngoc et al. (2014). A constant hydraulic head was imposed on lateral boundaries, which were considered adiabatic for heat transfer. Fluid flow was solved in steady state (with transient temperature transport) as data on storage capacity was unavailable. Doublets were modelled as a 1D vertical boundary of constant temperature (8°C) and constant flow (corresponding to the yearly mean of pumping flow needed to respond to heat demand). DBHE were modeled as 1D vertical boundary with imposed heat flux (varying monthly to reproduce the heat requirements). The heat requirement was equally divided between nodes of the DBHE. Mass transport and thermal conductivity dependence on temperature and pressure were not considered.

3. Results

Two types of systems appear technically feasible when considering mean hydraulic and thermal properties: 1) an open loop system with a spacing of 200 m between pumping and injection and 2) a DBHE, with 3 wells to

provide the required 780 kW. However, the sensitivity study showed that if permeability falls on the lower side of expected values, pumping and reinjecting in the open loop would require too much power to be technically possible (Fig 1).

Fig 1 Sensitivity of thermal breakthrough for an open loop system in the Cairnside unit with 200 m between pumping and injection. Numbers over hydraulic conductivity correspond to maximum drawdown (m) after 30 years of operation. Numbers over basal temperature correspond to the mean pumping rate (m^3/d).

4. Discussion

The preliminary models, developed at an early stage of a PhD thesis, used simplified geometry, properties and physics. Further work will use more complex models and specific properties to the Bécancour area, including historical data on brine extraction. Overlying units with reservoir potential (Beekmantown, Trenton), as well as different DBHE configurations, will also be considered.

5. Conclusions

The simulated open loop system within the Cairnside Formation appears to be the simplest design to meet the heat requirement. However, its feasibility is highly dependent on the permeability of the unit, which is known to be heterogenous (Tran Ngoc et al. 2014). Further work will offer insights into the performance of the different geothermal system, based on investigation of the formation properties and numerical modelling of various designs.

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